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Small Business Financing Mechanisms by Commercial Banks

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Abstract

Banks play an important role in the rapid development of small business and private entrepreneurship in our country, as the financial stability of entities is ensured as a result of loans provided by banks to small businesses. Small business provides high rates of resource turnover as a low-cost economic activity in the context of capital shortage. The article discusses the introduction and improvement of new forms of financing small business activities by commercial banks. On the basis of econometric analysis, the influence of loans provided by commercial banks on the economic development of small businesses and private entrepreneurship are studied, and ways to improve and expand the financing mechanisms for small businesses are also outlined.

Keywords: small business and private entrepreneurship, credit, microcredit, financing mechanism, capital, credit system, econometric modeling, regression, financial support.

Introduction

Economic reforms are being implemented consistently in our country. The formation and development of new economic, financial, social and other relations based on the market economy is the result of reforms. Today, small business and private business entities occupy an important place in the economic and social development of the country. Among the production entities, small business has the ability to quickly and easily adapt to the changing conditions of the external and internal environment. This feature gives impetus to the development of the competitive environment, the implementation of the processes of structural reconstruction of the economic system, and the development of production systems based on innovative technologies. Considering that small business entities help to positively solve the problem of social employment and reduce social tension in the society, it is of great importance to improve the current financing mechanism for supporting small business entities.

In the strategy of actions on the five priority directions of the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021, adopted by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on February 7, 2017 "On the Strategy of Actions for Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan", "deepening the reform of the banking system and ensuring stability, banks increasing the level of capitalization and the deposit base, strengthening their financial stability and reliability, further expanding lending to promising investment projects and small business and private entrepreneurship" was defined as one of the most important priorities. Banks have a great role in the rapid development of small business and private entrepreneurship, because the financial, economic and social aspects of ensuring economic development through the loans provided by banks to business entities are envisaged. It is known that small business, as an economic activity that does not require a lot of funds, provides high rates of resource turnover in the conditions of capital shortage, solves the problem of the formation of the consumer market and its filling in the conditions of economic restructuring, economic instability and limited resources in a quick and economical way. Small businesses immediately adapt to changes in consumer demand and thus provide the necessary balance in the consumer market.

In the following years, banking activity will be directed to solving the following priority tasks set before commercial banks:

- increasing financial stability in accordance with international norms and standards;
- strengthening of investment activities and capitalization level of the bank;
- further expansion of the bank's participation in financial support of small business and private entrepreneurship;
- To increase the financing of projects of small business and private business entities, to further expand the attraction and utilization of credit lines of international financial institutions; - strengthening the resource base, introducing new attractive types of savings and deposits, as well as widely attracting free funds of the population and economic entities to bank circulation by issuing debt obligations;
- to increase the variety and quality of the provided banking services through the use of advanced information and communication technologies, as well as the development of electronic commerce and the expansion of the cashless settlement system using bank plastic cards;
- development of new segments of the market in promising sectors of the economy, including services and tourism, industry, construction, participation in the financing of enterprises operating in free economic zones of the country;
- improving and optimizing the work of the bank's structural units by automating business processes and standardizing bank products, as well as introducing a system of management reports and analytical solutions.

Also, special attention will be paid to the financing of young entrepreneurs who have graduated from educational institutions, family business entities, as well as other promising socially important projects that serve to increase the economic potential of our country.

The bank's own credit resources, credit lines of international financial institutions, in particular the Islamic Corporation for the Development of the Private Sector, serve as sources of financing for long-term perspective projects of small business enterprises.

In the next year, the bank plans to continue work on introducing new banking products and technologies in the lending process, taking into account the best local and foreign experiences.

The bank considers investment activities to be one of its promising directions and plans to implement several works to increase the bank's investment flows in 2020, as well as to raise the quality of investment resources. One of the urgent tasks is to expand the activities of the financial companies to which the Bank has invested, and especially the acquisition of more attractive market segments by these companies.

Commercial banks will develop and implement a set of measures aimed at the use of new forms of small business financing, as well as the development and expansion of the activities of small business entities, as well as increasing their activity and efficiency. The issuance activity of the bank is focused on strengthening the long-term resource base of the bank by issuing and selling debt securities. In particular, the next issuance of deposit certificates is planned to strengthen the stable resource base. Issuance of securities should create an opportunity for the bank to expand and diversify the bank's loan resources and provide an alternative offer for the placement of their free funds to all of the bank's customers (including non-large customers).

In the following year, consistent work was carried out by the bank to create a modern infrastructure and to form processes for the development and expansion of activities in currency and money markets.

In accordance with the bank development strategy, commercial banks are planning to implement new forms of small business financing in the following year:

- to offer customers attractive banking services in the field of conversion, banknote transactions, as well as to expand the scope and types of services by conducting various marketing activities to increase the interest of customers in forex operations;
- carrying out activities to increase the business activity of the bank in the money and foreign exchange markets, as well as increase the recognition of the bank;
- use of new forms of small business financing, as well as participation in the projects of various institutions of the financial market and cooperation with them in the field of development of small business entities;
- small business financing by the bank, as well as improvement of the dealing operations processes of small business entities through the development of new modules, as well as the development of a special mobile application for conducting forex transactions with individuals.

The organizational-economic, theoretical-methodical aspects of the development of internal opportunities, conflicts and their financing mechanisms capable of ensuring the effective resolution of economic interests, goals and specific tasks in small business activity have been widely discussed by foreign and domestic scientists. At a time when the possibilities of obtaining credit for small business entities in the countries of the world became a problem, the mechanisms of crediting of start-up projects of the population were based on Stiglitz and Weisslar. Patersen, Rajan, Bergae Elsas, etc. conducted a study on the financial support and lending system based on reduced terms based on the assessment of the relationship of small business entities with banks, state organizations and small business support organizations. Feldman and Master conducted studies on issues of econometric modeling aimed at studying

the problems related to small business financing, the financial condition of enterprises in determining their creditworthiness, the level of development, and determining the creditworthiness of the creditor. In order to improve the financing of the activities of small business entities, I. Alimardonov made suggestions on reducing the costs related to their import fees.

In recent years, as a result of large-scale reforms implemented in the economy of Uzbekistan on financial support of small business and private entrepreneurship, the volume of loans and microfinance services provided by commercial banks to this sector is growing year by year. In particular, the volume of credit resources allocated to small businesses and private enterprises from all sources in 2019 amounted to 19,564.0 billion soums. amounted to 3.2 times compared to 2017, and the volume of microcredits increased by 3.6 times to 4015.0 billion soums. In particular, in 2019, 490.3 billion soums will be allocated for the development of family entrepreneurship and crafts. 2,782.2 billion soums for the development of women's entrepreneurship. 3381.4 billion soums to food production enterprises. 3915.8 billion soums to enterprises producing non-food consumer products. 360.2 billion soums for financing business projects of vocational college graduates. loan funds were allocated in the amount of soums.¹

In the practice of countries with a developed financial market, the funds of credit organizations are the main source of financing for the development of small businesses. Funds of commercial banks make up a large share of financing of small business and private entrepreneurship.

It is necessary to define targeted strategies aimed at further expansion of the practice of lending to small businesses and private enterprises by commercial banks. Also, the fact that lending to small business entities focuses on high liquid availability prevents further increase in the volume of lending to small business entities. This is because most small businesses do not have the highly liquid collateral that banks require. Another problem that is waiting to be solved in the practice of lending investment costs of small business entities is the high cost of investment loans attracted through foreign credit lines.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The lack of resource capacity for small business lending in banks has a negative impact on the stability of cash flows of all economic entities, including small business entities. This means that the economy's low liquidity level does not allow solving the problem of non-payment between economic entities. It is planned to provide more than 3 trillion soums of subsidies in 2021 within the framework of entrepreneurship programs in our country. In addition, 250 billion soums are planned to be allocated to the Employment Assistance Fund and the Public Works Fund.

Also, the main attention in lending to small business entities is focused on the availability of highly liquid collateral objects, which prevents further increase in the volume of lending to small business entities. This is because most small businesses do not have the highly liquid collateral that banks require.

Another problem that is waiting to be solved in the practice of lending investment costs of small business entities is the high cost of investment loans attracted through foreign credit lines.

The lack of resource capacity for small business lending in banks has a negative impact on the stability of cash flows of all economic entities, including small business entities. This means that the economy's low liquidity level does not allow solving the problem of non-payment between economic entities.

Taking into account the above, the following should be done to increase the role of banks in the development of small business and private business entities:

- taking into account the lack of highly liquid collateral objects in small business entities, increasing attention to lending them on the basis of leasing, refundable leasing and property liability insurance;

- in order to increase the volume of low-interest loans provided by commercial banks to small business entities, to increase the share of the state in the authorized capital of banks and to direct these resources to preferential lending to small business entities;
- optimization of the mechanisms of using free funds of large enterprises and organizations, taking into account the shortage of resources for short-term lending to small businesses by commercial banks;
- introduction of a calendar sequence of payments for these entities in order to reduce the level of credit risk arising from overdraft and overdraft lending to small business entities.

The practical implementation of our proposal to increase the efficiency of lending to small business entities by commercial banks will allow to significantly increase the volume of lending to them.

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